

International Seminar

Tides of Connections and Tensions

Revisiting the Indian Ocean and Red Sea as Spaces of Historical Entanglement

5 - 6 February, 2026
Online

Programme

Themes and scope

The Indian Ocean and the Red Sea have long been dynamic spaces of exchange, conflict and cultural integration, where empires, merchants, migrants and ideas have converged and clashed. This international seminar seeks to interrogate these maritime regions as active agents in shaping local, regional, and global histories, and challenges traditional narratives by foregrounding connectivity, friction, and durability across time and space.

The seminar argues that the Indian Ocean and the Red Sea should be understood not merely as arenas of contemporary geopolitical competition, but as spaces where long-standing maritime traditions and patterns of connectivity are re-emerging. It explores how these renewed forms of thalassocracy unfold within radically transformed geopolitical contexts, challenging conventional notions of maritime sovereignty and calling for new analytical frameworks to understand oceanic governance today.

The papers presented in the seminar reflect a wide range of disciplinary perspectives, including history, political science, and the social sciences, and engage scholars at different career stages. Particular attention is given to contributions by PhD candidates and early career researchers, with a notable presence of scholars working on or from the Indian Ocean and Red Sea regions.

The seminar brings together works-in-progress and fosters an open, collaborative discussion format. The panels prioritize original, unpublished work, encouraging the presentation of emerging research agendas and innovative approaches.

5 February

10.00-10.20am CET / 2.30-2.50pm IST

Welcome and Valedictory Message

Chair: Venkatanarayanan S. - CHRIST (Deemed to be University)

Maria Alessandra Panzanelli Fratoni - University of Turin, Deputy Head for Internationalisation, Department of Historical Studies)

Jose CC - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Vice Chancellor

10.20am-12.20pm CET / 2.50-4.50pm IST

Panel 1: Tales of Networks and Encounters

Chair: Sara Zanotta - University of Turin

Jenia Mukherjee, Agrima Mishra (Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur), *Environmental Archive of Myth and Memory: Early Modern (More-than-human) Histories from the Mouth of the Bay of Bengal*

Marcella Simoni (Ca' Foscari University of Venice, NYU Florence, European University Institute), *Ink, Identity, and Exchange: Jewish Presses Bridging the Mediterranean and Indian Ocean 1880s-1940s*

Samuel Emaha Tsegai (Queen's University), *Indigenous Merchant Cartographers and European Geographers: Trade Routes and Making and Circulation of Geographical Knowledge in the 19th Century Ethiopia*

Debalina Das (Central University of Kashmir), *Post-Maritime Consciousness and the Afterlife of Red Sea Legacies in Leila Aboulela's "Coloured Lights"*

Break - 12.20-12.30pm CET / 4.50-5.00pm IST

12.30-2.30pm CET / 5.00-7.00pm IST

Panel 2. Maritime Dynamics and Emerging Orders

Chair: Moin S. Hakak - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore

Federico Donelli (University of Trieste), *Entangled Seas and Shores: The Rise of a Hybrid Security Complex in the Red Sea-Western Indian Ocean*

Arnab Das (Maritime Research Center, Pune), *Indian Ocean Region in the New Global Order - A New Perspective Based on the Underwater Domain Awareness Framework*

Sara Cosatti (University of Trieste), *From the Highlands to the Sea: Ethiopia's Aims within the Emerging Indo-Pacific Order*

Dona Ganguly (Bhawanipur Education Society, Calcutta University), *Maritime Dynamics of India's Act East Policy: The Indian Ocean Perspective*

Vijay Sakhuja (India Council of World Affairs, New Delhi), *Cholas': The Front Runners of India's Maritime Strategy*

6 February

10.00am-12.00pm CET / 2.30-4.30pm IST

Panel 3. Local Actors in a Connected Red Sea-Indian Ocean

Chair: Alka S. Yadav - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore

Nicola Melis (University of Cagliari), *Hodeidah as a Maritime Contact Zone: Ottoman Governance, Local Networks, and Red Sea Entanglements (1850-1918)*

Anmol Mukhia (South Asian University, Delhi), *Classical Geopolitical Perspectives on Trade and Security in the Indian Ocean-Red Sea Region*

Viola Pacini (University of Bologna), *Regional Shifts and Local Adaptations: The Careers of Two Baluchi Enslavers (1930s-1940s)*

Jubin Easow Abraham (University of Kerala, Trivandrum), *Chains and Confluences: Traversing the Entangled Lives within the Transoceanic and Indigenous Slave Systems in Dutch Cochin*

Sama Hany Farouk Darwish (Mansoura University), *The Effect of the Nationalization of the Suez Canal on the Reshaping of Trade Networks in the Red Sea and Indian Ocean in the Post-Colonial Era*

Break - 12.00-12.10pm CET / 4.30-4.40pm IST

12.10-2.10pm CET / 4.40-6.40pm IST

Panel 4. Trading Routes and Strategic Nodes

Chair: Rohini Panicker - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore

Tilottama Mukherjee (Syamaprasad College, University of Calcutta), *The Indian Ocean and Southeast Asia: Analyzing the Inter-connectedness*

Beatrice Nicolini (Catholic University of the Sacred Heart, Milan), *Gwadar: The Strategic Gem Shaping the Future of Southwest Asia*

Kaustav Ghosh Roy (University of Delhi), *Ancient Bengal and Its Earliest River Networks and Maritime Trading Routes against the Backdrop of the Bay of Bengal and the Indian Ocean Littoral Trade in South Asia*

Priyanka Chand (Pondicherry University), *Merchants Connecting Red Sea and Indian Ocean World*

Debankita Das (University of Hyderabad), *Cultural Mobility across the Bay of Bengal: A Case Study of Odisha's Coast-maritime Interaction*

Final Wrap Up

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2023 - 2027
DIPARTIMENTO
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Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

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- **Venkatanarayanan. S** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Sreemoyee Sarkar** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Shalini B.** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Annachiara Raia** - Leiden University
- **Jan Záhorský** - University of West Bohemia

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- **Alka S. Yadav** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Moin S. Hakak** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Rohini Panicker** - CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore
- **Sara Zanotta** - University of Turin
- **Tiziana Pasciuto** - University of Turin
- **Samraksha Mukund, Ayaan Dutta, Narean Thirumalai KK, Adhithya Narayanan** - Student Volunteers from 6BA POLS, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore

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